

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

An essential, primary relationship between NKTR and Xist.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We report here identification of the natural killer cell triggering receptor *NKTR* as a primary target of the Xist non-coding RNA. Xist NKTR interactions likely occurred through or centrally involved the Xist RNP complex component *PNISR*.

Citations

1. Zhao, M., Qin, T. and Huang, D., 2022. ACT001 inhibits the proliferation of non-small cell lung cancer cells by upregulating NKTR expression. *Thoracic Cancer*, 13(12), pp.1772-1782.